

GREEN MANAGEMENT AND ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE OF COMMERCIAL BANKS IN ENUGU METROPOLIS, NIGERIA

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Abstract: This study examined the relationship between green management and organizational performance of commercial banks in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to; ascertain the relationship between green energy and quality of service of commercial banks in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria and determine the relationship between green waste recycling and timeliness of commercial banks in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria. The study adopted a survey design. The population of the study was three hundred forty five (345). The sample size of 345 was adopted due to what previous authors found and small nature of the population. The study used purposive sampling procedure and structured questionnaire was used to select respondents. Correlation analysis tool was employed to test two formulated hypotheses. It was revealed that green energy had a significant positive relationship with quality of service of commercial banks in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria ($r = .321$, $pv=000<0.05$) and green waste recycling had a significant positive relationship with timeliness of commercial banks in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria ($r= .960$; $pv= 000<0.05$). Therefore, based on the findings, researcher also concluded that green management had significant positive relationship with organizational performance of commercial banks in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria. The study thus recommends that management of commercial banks should develop strategies like green energy and green waste recycling in order to build a more resilient and sustainable future for the upcoming organizations.

Keywords: Green Management, Organizational Performance, Green Energy, Waste Recycling, Commercial Banks

Introduction

For organizations to survive in any competitive environment, they are expected to improve the quality of their product and services at a better rate than business rivals do. In such an environment, organizational efficiency is a vital element for continuous improvement in product and service quality (Garlatti, *et al*, 2022; Sözbilir, 2024). In other words, organizational efficiency is a significant indicator by which the profitability of organizations is measured (Ghosh, *et al*, 2021). Organizational efficiency is concerned with the optimal use of resources consumed to accomplish a task or produce goods and services (Ritala, *et al*, 2023). It focuses on processes, policies, and strategies, which are required to guarantee that the use of scarce resources is achieved by continuous, cost reduction and sometimes going green (Javanmard & Hasani, 2022).

The term "green management" was coined at the turn of the twentieth century in response to growing need for economic development. Its origin in modern times can be traced to the middle of the 1960s and it is time for managers to adapt to the "greening" phenomenon and adopt them into its ideology and practice (Čekanavičius, Bazytė, & Dičmonaitė, 2024). It incorporates sustainable operational procedures, product and material sourcing, labor practices, and shipping techniques, as well as the utilization of renewable resources, and it makes itself accountable for the human resource side of its operations (Fields & Atiku, 2023).

However, why are we choosing green? Green is more than a hue in the rainbow. Going green is a strategy for some organizations and the broader society to modify their lifestyles. This entails implementing more eco-friendly improvements. It is worth noting that the plain truth is that when an individual does something that affects the globe, good or bad, he or she has the full ability to make decisions, allowing the individual to manage the influence caused. Additionally, another critical point is the significance of turning green (Matheus, *et al.*, 2023).

Today, more than ever before, people are willing to operate in an environmentally responsible way and they understand that they are part of society and should therefore adopt green practices in organizations (Goyal, 2023). Concern for the environment already started since 1990s. Organizations, businesses have taken action to reduce waste, pollution by establishing approaches and system for environment management like:- green building, green energy and green waste recycling which is called green management practices. Green management, according to Lee (2021), is a strategy adopted by an organization in order to establish environmental management methods with the purpose of safeguarding and monitoring environmental elements. The green management is a necessity of the twenty-first century, as it is reported in the newspapers on a daily basis that there is tremendous pressure on the natural resources of planet Earth due to the excessive consumption of natural resources as a raw material by industries and other commercial organizations. Scientists and environmentalists are debating the problem of ecological imbalances since the situation is so grave. Green management is a novel concept and is considered a crucial part of management practices. It is a revolutionary concept in the academic world as well as the practical world of management (Stojanoska, 2023).

It is necessary to create a positive green management of the commercial banks in the minds of her various publics through sustained green building, green energy and green waste recycling. The commercial banks must find ways to communicate the value and image of its programme to a global audience, although once aimed primarily at local, regional or national audiences' websites today must be designed to serve broader international aims (Ajayi & Ayodele, 2018). It is against this background that the researchers seek to examine the relationship between green management and organizational performance of commercial banks in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

In recent trends, the perspectives on the operations of commercial banks have broadened beyond quality of service and timeliness. As commercial banks work to be competitive in terms of quality of service and timeliness issues as well as improving operations in terms of flexibility, delivery, quality, and cost, understanding green management practices is crucial and should be given priority in the decision-making processes by company management.

Today implementation of green management is intended to increase the organizational performance and help to develop new technical and management competences that support environmental improvements and thus improve the sustainability of the commercial banks. Thus, commercial banks develop their employees through green management. The situation need for commercial to focus on establishing a high green management to green building, green energy and green waste against. The consequences of lack of green management include poor green building; low green energy and high level of green waste recycling issues can have negative impact on organizational performance as a result of imbalance sustainability, conflict priorities and continuity/consistency of commercial banks activities.

Despite that, far too little attention has been paid to the effects of green management on organizational performance especially in commercial banks. It is clear that research into the effects of green management on organizational performance of commercial banks in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria is currently underexplored, and this has amounted to few literatures focusing on this area in Nigeria. The implication of this is the lack of organizational performance plan in the commercial banks as well as other sectors. It is based on the problem that this study seeks to fill the gap, especially in commercial banks setting.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to explore the relationship between green management and organizational performance of commercial banks in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria. Specific objectives were to;

- i. Ascertain the relationship between green energy and quality of service of commercial banks in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria.
- ii. Determine the relationship between green waste recycling and timeliness of commercial banks in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria.

Significance of the Study

This study highlighted how the green management affects organizational performance of commercial banks in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria. This study provides results that can help commercial bank managers to develop and implement an effective green management strategy considering the performance of employees by making suitable decisions about the outcomes and procedures for the employees that can increase their employee quality of service and timeliness aspect of duty that will ultimately increase performance of employees in organization to achieve organizational goals. The findings of this study further help commercial authorities to notice what dimensions of organizational performance are most important in current era to increase organizational performance. Lastly, this study provided recommendations for approaches to be taken by management depending on the finding of this study.

The study also covered five (5) selected modern banks namely; United Bank of Africa Plc, First Bank of Nigeria Plc, Zenith Bank of Nigeria Plc, Access Bank of Nigeria Plc and Guaranty Trust Bank (GTB) all in Enugu metropolis. This study only focused on staff of the selected commercial banks with proves of dependent and independent variables. Meanwhile, dependent variable known as organizational performance was proxied into quality of service and timeliness while independent variable known as green management was proxied into green energy and green waste recycling.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Review

Green

Green' means environmental. Green today has become a buzz word only due to the corporate & the individuals understanding & awareness that the consumption levels of resources made by them are higher than what is available (Opatha & Arulrajah, 2024).

Management

The word 'management' has been given various meanings. Accordingly, it does not seem that there is any one definition of management that commands universal acceptance or application to all situations. Often authors define the word in ways that reflect their experiences or suit their circumstances (Ile, 2002).

Green Management

Haden, Oyler, & Humphreys, (2023) defined Green Management (GM) as an organization-wide process of applying innovation to achieve sustainability, waste reduction, social responsibility, and a competitive advantage via Continuous learning and development and by embracing environmental goals and strategies that are fully integrated with the goals and strategies of the organization. Green management is defined as the process inside a company that uses innovation to accomplish sustainability, waste reduction, social responsibility, and competitive advantage via continuous learning and improvement (Matheus et al., 2023).

Green Energy

Renewable energy is energy that is collected from renewable resources, which are naturally replenished on a human timescale, such as sunlight, wind, rain, tides, waves, and geothermal heat. The incentive to use 100% renewable energy, for electricity, transport, or even total primary energy supply globally, has been motivated by global warming and other ecological as well as economic concerns. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change has said that there are few fundamental technological limits to integrating a portfolio of renewable energy technologies to meet most of the total global energy demand. Renewable energy use has grown much faster than even advocates anticipated. At the national level, at least 30 nations around the world already have renewable energy contributing more than 20% of energy supply (REN, 2020).

Green Waste Recycling

Recycling is very important as waste has a huge negative impact on the natural environment. Harmful chemicals and greenhouse gasses are released from rubbish in landfill sites. Recycling helps to reduce the pollution caused by waste. Recycling reduces the need for raw materials so that the rainforests can be preserved. Recycling is the recovery of useful materials, such as paper, glass, plastic, and metals, from the trash to use to make new products, reducing the amount of virgin raw materials needed. Producing recycled white paper creates 74% less air pollution and 35% less water pollution than producing paper from virgin fibers. Using recycled cans instead of extracting ore to make aluminum cans produces 95% less air pollution and 97% less water pollution (REN, 2020).

Organizational Performance

Bernardin and Russel (2023), define performance as follows: "Performance is defined as the record of outcomes produced on a specified job function or activity during a time period". Robbins (2022), performance is the

answer to the question "what results are achieved by someone after doing something". Schemerson, Hunt and Osborn, (2021) say performance is the quantity and quality of achievement of tasks, whether done by individuals, groups or organizations. A more comprehensive opinion is delivered by Brumbrach as follows: "Performance means behaviours and results. Behaviours emanate from the performer and transform performance from abstraction to action. Not just the instruments for results, behaviours are also outcomes in their own right the product of mental and physical effort applied to tasks and can be judged apart from results." The indicators are quantity of work, quality of work, timeliness, cooperation and personal quality (Gable, 2020).

Conceptual Framework

The model in figure 2.5 explained the relationship between green management and organizational performance of commercial banks in Nigeria. In the model, it is shown that performance of commercial banks in Nigeria attracts and remains quality of service and timeliness as dependent variables.

Source: Adapted from Ile and Onyia (2024).

Figure 2.5: Model of Green Management and Organizational Performance of Commercial Banks

Theoretical Framework

Icek Ajzen Theory of Planned Behaviour was developed and modified by Bosnjak in 2021. The theory which sees behavior as a product of intentions and attitudes which are basically beliefs about a behavior as well as subjective norms which are beliefs about the attitudes of others toward behavior, has remained a popular theory in Management literatures. It was propounded in 1985. The theory predicts human behavior on the basis of personal attitudes; on the basis of subjective norms and on the basis of behavioural control as may be perceived. Bosnjak, Ajzen and Schmidt (2020) opine that human behavior is directed with the instrument of believes that are behavioural; believes that are normative as well as believes that are called control beliefs. Belief that is behavioural is that which has to do with the behavioural outcomes of the behavior. Believes that are described as normative have to do with those believes that anchor on the LaMorte (2022) maintains that this theory has over the years, been appropriately used to forecast and/or give explanation of various behaviours. The theory supposes that behavioural achievement is a function of motivation which is the intention as well as ability which is the behavioural control. In fact, this theory relates to this study which emphasizes energy control and waste management. People ought to exhibit sound behaviours over issues of energy, waste and even environmental health.

Empirical Review

Onwudiwe, et al (2019) examined green management and organizational effectiveness in Nigeria. The aim of this paper is to examine the effect of green management (GM) on organizational effectiveness. Reviewed literature was used to discuss various aspects of green management mainly renewable energy and waste recycling. The results showed waste recycling has a positive and significant effect on cost reduction and pollution reduction.

Mahyarni and Desrir (2019) investigated the effect of green management strategy and economy benefit toward performance of Sharia SMES to support Halal tourism destination in India. The result of the research shows that green management strategy variable have effects toward the increase of economic benefit of Sharia SMEs, and economic benefit and green management strategy variable have effects toward performance of Sharia SMEs.

Ekanem, et al (2023) ascertained green operation practice and organizational performance in selected manufacturing firms in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The goal of this study was to determine how green operation affected organizational performance in a selected Nigerian manufacturing companies in Akwa Ibom State. The study used a descriptive survey approach. The findings indicate that green manufacturing and design have a significant impact on organizational performance in specific Akwa Ibom State manufacturing enterprises.

Khare, et al (2023) carried out a study on the importance of green management and its implication in creating sustainability performance on the small- scale industries in India. Result: green management affects SSIs' sustainability performance due to stakeholder demand, knowledge, environmental uncertainty management, and product uniqueness, but not organisational resources.

Njoku, *et al* (2023) examined green management as a predictor of organizational outcomes in hospitality enterprises in Mbaise, The objectives of the study are to evaluate the level of correlation between pollution control and market share; assess the level of correlation between pollution control and employee retention; examine the level of correlation between waste management and market share; and to determine the relationship between waste management and employee retention in hospitality enterprises in Mbaise. The research adopts the survey research design. The paper revealed that pollution control and market share; pollution control and employee retention; waste management and market share; waste management and employee retention in hospitality enterprises in Mbaise, have positive and significant relationships.

Elshaer, *et al* (2023) evaluated green management and sustainable performance of small and medium-sized hospitality businesses: moderating the role of an employee's pro-environmental behavior. It was a survey research. The study used the Smart PLS-structural equation modeling technique to analyze data. It was found that green management improved environmental, economic and social performance of businesses.

Yanto, *et al* (2023) examined imposing green management to enhance the organizational awareness against the environmental sustainability in India. The sample of the study is the province of Indonesia; North Sumatera and purposive sampling method was used to sample the population. PLS methodology is used to analyze the data. Findings reveal that green management positively impacts organizational awareness, environmental concern and green technology.

Loknath, and Abdul (2024) examined green management concept and strategies in Malaysia. There are far reaching repercussions of human industrial activities resulting in the extinction and endangering of many life forms. Hence, this paper attempts to provide a basic overview of the concept of green management at the introductory level and discuss different types of green management strategies adopted by organisations.

Gaps in Empirical Review

The current study is aimed at investigating green management on organizational performance of commercial banks in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria. Literature published on this subject area by various scholars has been reviewed and gaps have been identified like time (2024), variable, (green energy, green waste recycling against quality of service and timeliness), and geographical (Enugu, Nigeria) gaps. This research endeavored to bridge this gap by answering the research questions and analyzing hypotheses using correlation matrix posed in this study, therefore, this gap study stand to fill.

METHODOLOGY

The descriptive survey research design was used in this study. This design summarizes an existing phenomenon via the use of numbers to characterize individuals or groups and examines the nature of existing conditions (McMillan & Schumacher, 2020). Primary and secondary data were collected from staff using questionnaire, observation, internet and library as instrument for data collection. The entire staff formed the target population of this study with total of 345 of five (5) selected modern banks (Igwenagu, 2016). Based on the small number of the population 345, the researcher conveniently decided to use entire population as sample size determination in line with related studies who have done same. According to related study by Elshaer, *et al* (2023) who evaluated green management and sustainable performance of small and medium-sized hospitality businesses: moderating the role of an employee's pro-environmental behavior and even Yanto, *et al* (2023) who examined imposing green management to enhance the organizational awareness against the environmental sustainability in India. Purposive sampling technique was used in identifying and reaching sample for this study. This is because the study sought to find views of staff that had better knowledge of green management and could comment better on organizational performance.

Structured questionnaire was adopted. The copies of questionnaire were designed so as to provide answers to the objectives of the study after analysis. Questionnaire surveys have been proposed by Chen and Jin (2018) as most broadly adopted approach in quantitative research. The structured questionnaires employed largely closed ended questions to ensure uniformity in responses. The questionnaire was designed to address the research aim, objectives and the researcher questions of this study. The questionnaire comprised two main sections. Section A of the questionnaire covered the demographic data of the respondents whilst section B covered green management and organizational performance. Five-point Likert scale questions were mainly used on a scale of 1-5 which was rated on a scale of 1 to 5: where 1= strongly agree; 2= agree; 3= undecided; 4= disagree; 5= strongly disagree (Alston and Miller, 2021). The primary data collected from the respondents were analyzed using several tools of analysis like the Descriptive Statistics (Percentages, Means, Frequencies and Standard Deviations), and Mean score ranking. Software applications used for the analysis of quantitative data were the Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS), using correlation analysis. Formula for correlation analysis:

$$r = \frac{n \sum xy - \sum x \sum y}{\sqrt{[n (\sum x^2) - (\sum x)^2][n (\sum y^2) - (\sum y)^2]}}$$

Coefficient of determination r^2

Formula for regression

$$Y_i = f(X_i \beta) + e_i$$

- X = dependent variable
- F = function
- X₁ = independent variable
- β = coefficient

Test of Hypotheses

Test of Hypothesis One

H₀₁: There is no positive relationship between green energy and quality of service of commercial banks in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria.

H_{a1}: There is positive relationship between green energy and quality of service of commercial banks in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria.

Table 1: Analysis of Correlation

Correlations			
		Green Energy	Quality of Service
Green Energy	Pearson Correlation	1	.321**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	300	300
Quality of Service	Pearson Correlation	.321**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	300	300

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Extracted from SPSS Version 0.25

From the correlation result shown above, there was bivariate significant positive relationship between green energy and quality of service with a probability value of .000 and $r = .321$ which indicates that there was significant positive relationship between green energy and quality of service of commercial banks in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria.

Tests for Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: There is no positive relationship between green waste recycling and timeliness of commercial banks in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria.

H_{a2}: There is positive relationship between green waste recycling and timeliness of commercial banks in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria.

Table 2: Analysis of Correlation

Correlations		Green waste recycling	Timeliness
Green waste recycling	Pearson Correlation	1	.460**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	300	300
Timeliness	Pearson Correlation	.460**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	300	300

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Extracted from SPSS Version 0.25

From the correlation result shown above, there was bivariate relationship between green waste recycling and timeliness with a probability value of .000 and $r = .960$ which indicates that there was a significant positive relationship between green waste recycling and timeliness of commercial banks in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria.

Summary of Findings

- i. Green energy had a significant positive relationship with quality of service of commercial banks in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria ($r = .321$, $pv=000<0.05$).
- ii. Green waste recycling had a significant positive relationship with timeliness of commercial banks in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria ($r= .960$; $pv= 000<0.05$).

Conclusion

Based on findings under study, the study concludes that green management had significant positive relationship with organizational performance of commercial banks in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria. Meanwhile, Businesses that think about how to implement green management dimensions are likely to be more ecologically friendly, save money, use less, and implement green from the very beginning. Reducing resource use, energy use, waste production, and emissions of pollutants and greenhouse gases is the main objective of green manufacturing. It tries to minimize the emission of dangerous substances by emphasizing the effective use of resources such as energy, water, and raw materials.

Recommendations

It was recommended that commercial banks in Nigeria's specially Enugu State should use these green management concepts. Management of commercial banks should develop strategies like green energy and green waste recycling in order to build a more resilient and sustainable future for the upcoming organizations.

Contributions to Knowledge

Firstly, the study will contribute to the existing knowledge on green management and organizational performance. Considering, the literature expansion that was made by the researcher. The expectation is either the finding of this study support the theory or contradicts it, which will in turn ground the applicability of the theories mentioned and other stakeholders may use the findings of this study as a guide in formulating policies that will serve as a tool for decision making.

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